

NOT FORGOTTEN

(The destiny of some and their heroism)

Righteous Among the Nations

„Whoever saves one life, saves the world entire“

Deeds for the sake of brotherly love

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- Photos:** from the private archives of the families that received medals of recognition.

- October 6, 1938* – Žilina agreement was accepted concerning the Slovak autonomy.
- November 4, 1938* – two days after Vienna arbitration, the Slovak autonomous government ordered transportation of indigent Jews from Slovakia to the territory that was ceded to Hungary. Forcibly removed from their homes, and money and values taken from them., the Jews were interned in inhuman conditions for weeks.
- February 5, 1939* – radical populists Alexander Mach and Karol Murgaš called for a radical solution of the Jewish question in the Guardist Manifesto in Rišňovice.
- March 14, 1939* – Slovak state was established due to the significant intervention from Adolf Hitler. After the adoption of the constitution, the name agreed upon was the “Slovak Republic.”
- April 18, 1939* – the government passed its first anti-Jewish regulation – the definition of who is a Jew.
- April 25, 1940* – the Diet of Slovak Republic passed into law article 113/1940 Sl., the so-called First Aryanization Law.
- September 3, 1940* – the Diet of Slovak Republic was passed as a constitutional law (valid for 1 year), which entitled the government to take necessary actions for complete exclusion of Jews from economic and social life. In 1940, all Jewish groups and associations were dismissed, except for religious communities and the Jewish Centre was established as the only organization acting on behalf of the Jews that was recognized by the officials. In November 1940, many Jewish families had to move out from the city centres to abandoned houses in the outskirts of the cities. During the 1940/41 school year, Jewish pupils and students were excluded from state and public schools. Jewish schools were prevalent and education continued in very unpleasant conditions in temporary buildings.
- November 30, 1940* – the Slovak Republic’s government passed another regulation, article 303/1940 Sl. law this time concerning Jewish companies, the so-called Second Aryanization Law. In the following year, 1941, dozens of Jewish companies and workshops were destroyed and some of them were later put into operation by non-Jewish businessmen (this was the purpose of Aryanization). With hundreds of Jewish men having been prevented from making a living, they were compelled to be taken into forced labour. Many families without a means of earning a living became dependent on support from the Jewish Centre and the religious community.
- April 2, 1941* – a regulation of the Ministry of Interior established Jewish labour camps and centres.
- September 9, 1941* – the Slovak Republic’s government passed yet another regulation, article 198/1941 Sl., a law concerning the lawful status of the Jews, so-called “Jewish codex.”
- December 2, 1941* – Slovak Prime Minister Vojtech Tuka negotiated with Hans Ludin (a German officer in Slovakia) about the transportation of Jews from Slovakia to the Generalgouvernement (today’s Poland).
- March 25, 1942* – by order of the Slovak Prime Minister Vojtech Tuka, the first transport from Poprad was sent illegally (1,000 young women and girls from the Šariš-Zemplin County to German concentration camps in Poland.
- April 11, 1942* – the first transportations of families began (other than the girls/women who were taken earlier)
- May 15, 1942* – the Parliament of Slovak Republic adopted a constitutional law about evacuation of Jews, which retrospectively legalized deportations.
- October 20, 1942* – the first phase of deportations was completed, during which 58,000 Jews were deported from Slovakia.
- September 30, 1944* – the second phase of deportation of Jews from Slovakia began.
- March 31, 1945* – the last transport of Jews left Slovakia. In this phase, 13,500 Jews were deported.

„Solving the Jewish Question“ in Slovakia.

The national-socialist politics of racial superiority introduced a new dimension of anti-semitism in the Slovak society, which had begun in the 19th century. It acquired its monstrous dimensions during the period of the 1st Slovak Republic, 1939-1945. "Solving the Jewish Question" in Slovakia became a veritable trauma of modern Slovak history. Moral consequences of this shameful act are visible in today's society. The dramatic fate of approximately 89,000 Jews -- men, women and children -- is the souvenir of Slovak nationalism. Crimes against humanity during the Second World War were executed in an unspeakable manner.

The anti-Jewish campaign began in 1938, after the pronouncement of Slovakia's autonomy. The introduction of the concept of "Solving the Jewish Question" became one of the main drivers of the governing politics of the newly-established authoritarian-totalitarian regime. During the night between the 4th to 5th of November, the autonomous government with the help of the Hlinka Guard troops, violently evacuated and deported the inconvenient Jews to the south of Slovakia, which after the Vienna Arbitration, belonged to Hungary at the time. The repressions started after that incident.

The establishment of the Slovak State on 14th of March 1939 (naming itself the Slovak Republic, according to the July 1939 constitution) created a spirit of nationalism. The authoritative-totalitarian regime expressed itself through antidemocratic, anti-human and even antichristian actions.

Consistent with the anti-Semitic politics of the government, official propaganda generated hatred towards Jewish citizens. After the Slovak-German negotiations in Salzburg in the summer of 1940, the destiny of thousands of Jews was determined according to the German model, based on racial principles. A special German advisor for "the solution of Jewish question", Dieter Wisliceny, arrived in Slovakia. In September 1940, the Slovak parliament gave full power to the government of the First Slovak Republic to solve the Jewish question within one year. The German advisor proposed a simple plan of taking away the earnings and property of Jewish citizens. With parliament granting the government greater strength, hundreds of anti-Jewish regulations and public notices of central or regional character were formulated.

The actions of the government systematically excluded Jewish citizens from economic and public life. It premeditatedly deprived them of social, civil and eventually, their human rights. By September 1941, the Jewish community was impoverished according to plan and this disenfranchised mass of people became an inconvenient social burden of the state.

The peak of the events occurred on September 9, 1941 with the issue of government regulation number 198/1941 Sl. z., the so-called "Jewish Codex". This regulation contained as many as 270 paragraphs and was the broadest regulation issued during the period of the First Slovak Republic. It was an exact copy of German laws used against Jews and it finalized the solution of the Jewish question in Slovakia based on strict racial principles. The laws aimed at the Jewish citizens resulted in tragic consequences in early 1941, as the preparations for their eviction from Slovakia began.

The first transport carrying a thousand of young people left on March 25, 1942 to the Auschwitz concentration camp in occupied Poland. The government, led by the radical Vojtech Tuka, carried out the deportations based on article 22. § of the Jewish Codex concerning their labor duties. Officially they were sent to Poland to work. By May 1942, when parliament accepted a law about eviction, it began with the words: "It is possible to evict the Jews from the territory of Slovak Republic." Immigrants lost all their movable property (they no longer had immovable property) and/or citizenship. The cost of eviction of one person was 500 Reich marks and the evictors were reimbursed from the Jewish property, which was confiscated.

By the end of the transports in 1942, 58,000 people had been deported from Slovakia.

The deportations were accompanied by violence. The inhumane treatment of the Jewish population caused justifiable outrage by the general public as well as among the church representatives. A large number of the Jews were rescued before deportation thanks to the self-sacrifice of Slovak citizens, church and state representatives who disagreed with the methods of the government officials and they pressed to stop the transports and succeeded in October 1942. As a result, Jews were not deported from Slovakia until 1944 in spite of pressure from Germany. This changed after the occupation of Slovakia by the German army in August 1944. In cooperation with the emergency unit of Hlinka Guard, another 13,500 Jews were deported. Almost all of the deported died under the inhumane conditions of the Nazi camps.

The honor of the nation, which firstly impoverished the Jews and then sent tens of thousands of them to certain death in concentration camps, was saved by some of the Slovak inhabitants with their heroic attitude. Many of them are the awardees of the title "Righteous Among the Nations".

ThDr. Peter Borza, PhD

YAD VASHEM

In 1953, Israel's parliament, the Knesset, passed the Yad Vashem Law, establishing the Yad Vashem Institute and initiating the Righteous Among the Nations program. The latter defines and recognizes people who unselfishly risked their lives to save Jews, rewarding them with a medal in his or her own name, a certificate of honor, having the name added to those on the Wall of Honor in the Garden of the Righteous.

A complex procedure exists for accepting a rescuer as a Righteous Among the Nations. An independent commission of volunteers considers the documented testimonies and a retired Supreme Court judge confirms the decision. He is guided by the motto: "Whoever saves one life, saves the world entire", that comes from the Talmud.

It would be difficult to create a single prototype profile for a Slovak citizen to be worthy of the title of "Righteous Among the Nations". Similar to Righteous Among the Nations from other countries, even in Slovakia these generous people came from different social, ideological or religious groups, as well as service levels within the regime. Not even education was a deciding factor. It was only necessary to understand and empathize with the feeling of human suffering and be willing to do something about it.

There came a point in time when a Jew could only save him/herself in Slovakia with the help of non-Jews. Not even the illegal Jewish group, which was organised in Bratislava at that time to help those in hiding with financial support and fake documents, could manage without the help of non-Jews.

Who were those random people, who had the courage to provide help to those, caught in death traps, even in dangerous circumstances? They were neither saints, nor fearless heroes. They were common people from all areas of life: farmers and craftsmen; the educated and illiterate; doctors and ex-patients of Jewish doctors; religious and secular people, priests and Communists; close and distant acquaintances; friends and total strangers; former servants, babysitters of Jewish children; merchants, who didn't hesitate to deliver groceries for free to hidden and penniless people. And the list goes on.

Many of those, who unhesitatingly provided shelter to the desperate in their hopeless status, were the people who had finished only several years of public school, living in poverty themselves. But in many cases, these were people with a virtuous soul. Thanks to their great humanity they became symbols of morality.

Dr. Gila Fatranová

Yad Vashem Museum in Israel – a memorial for martyred people and heroes of the State of Israel during the Holocaust is the best-known memorial of the annihilation of Jews. It was established in 1953 and is located in Jerusalem. In 1963, the Israel Yad Vashem Museum started to bestow the title "Righteous Among The Nations" to people from all around the world, who risked their lives to save Jews during the Holocaust. The project is one of its kind in the world. Everyone, thus awarded, plants a tree in Avenue of the Righteous Among The Nations on top of the mountain (Hazikaron) in Jerusalem as an essential universal symbol of life.

A person who is nominated for the award "Righteous Among The Nations", is given a specially created medal with his name and a quotation from the Talmud, from the Traktat Sanhedrin: "whoever saves one life, saves the world entire". Besides this, the awardee is given a certificate of honour, and his name is placed on 'The Wall of Honour' in the Garden of the Righteous in Yad Vashem in Jerusalem. If the honouree is no longer alive, the award is given to his/her closest relatives in the ceremony in Israel or in their country through the embassy and representatives of the State of Israel.

GOD IS LOVE, LET'S LOVE HIM
Bishop's saying of blessed Pavol Peter Gojdič, OSBM

Righteous Among the Nations since January 27, 2008
Blessed bishop of Prešov

Pavel Peter GOJDIČ, OSBM
(1888-1960)

He openly protested against deportations and he saved the lives of dozens of Slovak Jews

He was among the few who realized the impending tragedy which had already begun by the creation of a commission to develop the program of "solving the Jewish question" in January 1939. In a pastoral letter sent to priests of his church, he warned against nationalism, chauvinism and racism – against ideologies that discriminate against certain people – because before God everyone is equal. He foresaw that these ideologies would cause a lot of evil and misfortune.

Dr. Gila Fatranová

Gojdič reacted to the ideas of nationalistic ideology via his pastoral letter of January 1939, in which he talked about the epidemic that had begun to spread in Europe. It found its victims also in Slovakia. At the time of his pastoral letter, the so-called 'Jewish Question' was being discussed. He considered it misleading and even dangerous for Slovakia, because when "someone wrongs another, he harms himself".

His clear understanding of the problem as early as January 1939 showed Gojdič's excellence, orientation, and desire to adhere to the concept of basic human rights. Brutal handling of vulnerable Jews during round-ups for transportations strongly affected him. He was not satisfied with the common practice of catholic bishops writing their memoranda and their declarations. In May 1942 he wrote a letter, addressed to chargé d'affaires Guisepe Burzi, describing the horrors of the transportations and he suggested that president J. Tiso resign. ("Barbarism which was committed on this poor nation rises higher than any inhumanity."). With this letter he also defended the interests of Catholic Church, whose reputation was in danger.

Bishop Gojdič with his clear attitude and active way also showed the proper way for clergy and believers; how they should behave toward suffering Jews. He helped them orientate themselves in a difficult time. To priest Michal Mašlej, who feared that with hiding the racially persecuted he jeopardized the safety of his parishioners, Gojdič said: "Helping persecuted people results from the love of close ones and therefore it is your obligation, to the best of your ability, to help and provide hiding for Jews, who are threatened with deportation."

P. P. Gojdič personified inner peace, humility, amazing modesty, kind-heartedness and love of God and neighbour.

On October 26, 1942 the director of the secret service (called 'Gestapo') informed the Ministry of Interior in writing about many cases of fake conversions. In the report, he wrote about cases where only one member of the family converted to Christian faith to save the whole family. Most of the converts remained faithful to Jewish religion; mostly in secret, but sometimes openly. It was found that 249 Jewish families converted to the Greek Catholic faith and 533 to orthodoxy. More than 1,500 Jewish lives were saved by this process.

Marianna Spitzerová, jedna zo zachránených

Rescued Jews confirmed in their testimonies that bishop Gojdič was courageous, fearless, full of humanity, and respected the rights to dignity of every human being. In spite of the inhuman spirit of contemporary society, he maintained the spirit full of humanity and true mankind. He confirmed that there are no apologies or excuses, when preserving human rights.

One of the rescued, Marianna Zachova, born Spitzerova, was twelve years old in 1942, when the deportations started. Gojdič placed Marianna and her sister Zuzana in the monastery residence of Basil the Great and also allowed them to attend a high school in Presov. "We lived a normal life without fear and danger," said Marianna in her testimony. Her father, Pavel Lukac-Spitzer was also in a dramatic situation. When the family was with the bishop in the city together, the Hlinka Guard just started rounding up Jews. Bishop Gojdič hugged him tightly around the shoulders and he protected him against the Guardists.

Erika Fleischerová with parents

Gojdič also rescued the Fleischers from a transport headed for a concentration camp. Erika Fleischer was only five years old then. For this heroic act he needed just a certificate of baptism, which he personally issued. Rescuee Erika kept this document until 2006, when she attached it to her testimony. It meant her whole family survived.

The ones rescued by the bishop, foresaw the establishment of the Communist regime after the war and advised him to emigrate to the West. Gojdič did not do so. Later the Communist regime hunted him, fabricated charges and sentenced him to life in prison, where he died on July 17, 1960, the day of his birthday.

On November 4, 2001, Pope Ján Pavol II declared bishop Gojdič as blessed.

Bishop Gojdič visiting Olšavica

He excelled in his love of God and people; even during his lifetime they called him the "bishop with the golden heart".

Righteous Among the Nations since June 18, 2007

Imrich ADAM

Saved the lives of:

**Dezider Grossmann, Alžbeta Grossmann,
Zuzana Grossmann**

Imrich Adam

Imrich Adam lived with his wife Ema and his two children in Sabinov. Ema's sister Alžbeta, a Catholic, was married to an ophthalmologist Dezider Grossmann, who started a practice in Košice in 1929. After annexation of Košice by the Hungarians, the Grossmanns settled in Prešov, where in 1943 their daughter, Zuzana, was born.

The Grossmanns moved to Sabinov at the end of August 1944. As Mr. Grossmann was in danger, Adam found a suitable hiding place in the woods, where he hid him. He provided him with the basics and brought him food on a regular basis. Occasionally Adam took him home, where he saw his wife Alžbeta and daughter Zuzana.

After the liberation of the Prešov district on January 20, 1945, Sabinov and other nearby areas were liberated too and the stress from hiding finally ended.

On June 18, 2007, Imrich Adam received the award Righteous Among the Nations from the Memorial Yad Vashem in Jerusalem.

Ema Adamová

*Daughter
Jozefína Adamová
and son Pavol Adam*

House of Imrich Adam still stands

*Saved spouses Dr. Dezider Grossmann
and Alžbeta Grossmann*

*Ema Adamová
and Imrich Adam*

Righteous Among the Nations from October 1, 1990

Vladimír ANTOL • Anka ANTOLOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

four members of the Goldman family

Friendly relations between Anka and Vladimir Antol and the Goldmanns existed before the war. Vladimir Antol, a teacher and the principal at a school in Slovenská Ves was also Dr. Goldmann's patient in Kežmarok.

After the outbreak of the Slovak national uprising, the Goldmann family were concerned about their safety. They decided to hide in the school building, where Antol lived with his family. Together, they dug a hole that allowed them to crawl directly from the apartment to the cellars, and thus created a hiding place for four people. Fear and worry escalated when Gestapo members settled in the school. Despite the danger they were in for harbouring Jews, the Antols never even considered moving their friends out of the house. Once after the war somebody asked Antol, what led him to take such a dangerous risk and to save a Jewish family, he replied: "I am a religious person. By saving a human life I will hopefully reserve a place in the world to come."

*Wedding photography
of the Antols from 1940*

Anka Antolová

After the war, the Goldmanns immigrated to Israel. They kept in touch by correspondence, but later it was stopped when Vladimir Antol was dismissed from work, sent to a labour camp and persecuted. Vladimir Antol died from his suffering in 1984.

School in Slovenská Ves during the war

Entrance of the school

*The family of the saved
Goldmanns during their visit
to Slovakia*

Righteous Among the Nations since 2005

Alexej BASÁR

Saved the lives of:

**Aladár Herz, his wife and children,
Ernest Herz with his fiancée Terézia**

At the time of Jewish deportation from eastern Slovakia, Aladár Herz was married and had three little children. His sister Terézia was engaged to his cousin Ernest Herz, a bakery owner from Prešov. A baker of the Ruthenian origin, Alexej Basára, became the aryanizer of the bakery. He was an expert in his profession but he lacked organization skills. That's why the authorities agreed that the original bakery owner, Ernest Herz, could continue to work in the bakery.

Alexej Basár gained an exception permit for Ernest Herz, which protected him from deportation, however, it didn't apply to his fiancée. When she had to leave, Ernest joined her. As soon as Basár learned that Ernst Herz had been put on a deportation train, he chased the train in a taxi. He caught the train near Prešov, at the Kysak station. He convinced the Hlinka Guardists to free Ernest and Terézia and returned with them back to Prešov. Alexej Basár immediately left for Bratislava, where, for a large sum of money, he managed to get the exceptions for Aladár Herz and his family who, at that moment, were located in the Poprad transit camp, prior to being sent to a concentration camp. Six members of Aladár's family, practically destined to death, returned home. Those six that Basár saved managed to survive both the first and the second wave of transportations. Some were hidden in Slovakia, some survived in concentration camps. When they returned home after liberation, Basár greeted them with joy and returned all their property to them.

Righteous Among the Nations since June 2, 1993

Emanuel TAKÁČ • Oľga TAKÁČOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

Erika Kardošová, Ružena Rozenfeldová

Erika Kardošová, with mother Ružena Rozenfeld were hidden in the house of the Takáč family in Prešov. In a modest-sized apartment rescuers arranged a space for "new friends". They managed to hide there for 7 months until the deportation in 1942. Emanuel Takáč, a village teacher, provided food for the ones in hiding and his wife Oľga stayed home and looked after not only their own seven children, but also those under their protection. One of the sons – Mikuláš, at that time a 16-year old, later a professor of medicine, as a service to the hidden, helped them keep in touch with relatives, who were hiding in the yard of the priest in Sabinov.

Emanuel and Olga Takáč

Righteous Among the Nations since March 16, 1992

Peter DUDINSKÝ

Saved the lives of:

the Schaechter family

The Schaechter and Dudinský families were neighbours in Podolíneč. Emil Schaechter had a small shop with staple goods in the village. His sister Malvína with her daughter also lived with them. Peter Dudinský was a Greek-Catholic priest in Ihľany, near Spišská Bela and was known for his religious tolerance.

On May 25, 1942 the news spread that the Hlinka Guard members and police from distant locations were coming and their task was to concentrate and deport Jews. The whole family thought they should try and run away. When the Schaechter family found themselves in need, Dudinský offered to help. He hid them in farmer Michael Forest's place and he was concerned about their safety during the whole time. A group of nineteen other Jews joined the Schaechters in hiding.

In early November Priest Dudinský and his assistant were arrested. Their arrest resulted in the detection of the Schaechter's bunker. The whole group was caught and deported to the Ravensbrück concentration camp.

After liberation, Emil found his mother alive in Slovakia. His first journey was to look for the good-hearted Slovaks, especially to P. Dudinský, to thank everyone for their noble deeds. After the establishment of the Communist regime, Dudinský and his church were persecuted. He died under the Communist oppression.

Peter Dudinský

Peter Dudinský with his wife and daughters

Peter Dudinský among believers

Peter Dudinský (1973)

Righteous Among the Nations since February 11, 1991

Štefan FRANK

Saved the lives of:

Ludwig Välder, Hedviga Välderová, Artúr Välder, Kornélia Välderová a Emerich Goldberger, Helena Goldbergerová, Terézia Goldbergerová, Eva Goldbergerová, Vierka Goldbergerová, Ladislav Šimovič, Anton Vacek, Zuzana Kurzová, three members of the Heršková family

Štefan Frank worked as an accountant at a sawmill, Lichtenstein & Vilček, in Hrabušice. After aryztation he became a director there. Välder was an employee at the company.

In 1942, when there was a danger of deportation, Frank obtained false documents for two of Välder's daughters and he placed both of them in a school institute of the Catholic monastery in Levoča.

With dramatic events in August 1944 associated with the termination of any exceptions and the threat of a death penalty to those who would provide shelter to Jews, Frank arranged for a place to hide in the mountains for the Välders (Ludwig, his wife Hedwiga, daughters Agnes, Erika and grandparents Arthur and Cornelius). He began to take care of them and brought them food. Also working in the sawmill was Emerich Goldberger, Frank's childhood friend. When they learned that Golberger's mother Teresa was arrested, Frank went to the city, rescued her and brought her back into Hrabušice to Emerich.

In early July 1944, five members of the Goldberger family (Emerich, Helena, Terézia, and daughters Eva and Vierka) were caught and escorted to the concentration facility in Sklené Teplice. Frank managed to rescue his friend's family illegally, but in early August the whole family of Goldbergers was recaptured. Frank managed to rescue them again and bring them all to Hrabušice.

Two political prisoners, refugees from Ilava, Dr. Ladislav Šimovič and Dr. Anton Vacek, joined the Välders in the bunker. Zuzana Kurzová, Frank's employee also moved into the bunker. At the time there was also a three-member Heršks family. After the occupation of Banská Bystrica by the Germans, Zuzana Kurzová, Välders' acquaintance, fled the city. Frank procured false documents for her and hired her in the sawmill. Altogether, Frank helped rescue 19 people.

Righteous Among the Nations since September 6, 1984

Karol KAMINSKÝ

Saved the lives of:

Alexander Staff

The connection between the rescuer Karol Kaminský and the rescued Alexander Staff, went back to the time when they were neighbors in Trebišov. Karol, who ran a branch of Baťa commerce brand, was a dedicated anti-fascist. Despite the fact that in 1942 he was transferred to Čierny Balog in central Slovakia, Karol and Alexander still remained in touch.

At the time of the deportations of Jews to Poland, Staff was taken to the concentration camp in Nováky. After six weeks he managed to escape from there. He returned to Trebišov, his native town, and with the help of Kaminský, he hid in various places. After the forced evacuation of Jews from eastern Slovakia to the west, in the spring of 1944, Kaminský provided him with original documents of one of his staff to be able to prove himself as an Aryan. With this identity, he moved to Balog, to be near his helper.

At the time when deportations of Jews started again, in 1944, Kaminský moved his protégé to his friend and a well-known farmer in one of the surrounding villages. Staff was hidden in the grain chamber, and once a day he was given food. When the winter started, Kaminský hid him in his basement, where he stayed until liberation.

Righteous Among Nations since January 12, 1994

Ján HRONČÁK • Mária HRONČÁKOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

Margita Immerblumová, Jozef Immerblum, Ilse Immerblumová, Ivan Immerblum, Imrich Hirschler

Mária Hrončáková

Margita and Jozef Immerblum and their children Ilse and Ivan lived in Špisské Podhradie during the war. Their father's "exception" saved them from deportations in 1942, according to which, "he was indispensable for the agriculture of the state". These cards were valid only temporarily, therefore, the Immerblums decided to protect themselves from deportations by getting baptism certificates.

They learned that the bishop of the Greek-Catholic Church, Gojdič encouraged his priests to provide baptism certificates to the persecuted. This information led the Immerblums to a local Greek-Catholic priest Michal Mašlej in the village of Olšavica, who promised to provide baptism certificates for them. During the baptism ceremony of twenty Jews he named local farmers as their "godfathers". For the Immerblums it was their rescuer Ján Hrončák. Mašlej in his masses asked believers to protect Jews in the name of "Jesus Christ's commands".

After the outbreak of the Slovak National Uprising in September 1944, the Immerblums decided to move to Olšavica. Jewish refugee Imrich (Meir) Hirschler from Poland joined them as well. After the plead of the priest Mašlej, the family of the "godfather" Hrončák was willing to hide both Immerblums and Hirschler, and dressed in farmers clothes, they survived until the liberation in January 1945.

Ján Hrončák

Righteous Among the Nations since September 4, 1991

Ján LEBDOVIČ • Žofia LEBDOVIČOVÁ

**Margita LEBDOVIČOVÁ • Anna LEBDOVIČOVÁ
Emília LEBDOVIČOVÁ**

Saved the lives of:

Maximilián Goldmann's family, Dr. Fried with his wife, Dr. Shick with his family

The Lebdovič family was poor and they lived in a small village of Mlynčeky, near Kežmarok. They had known the Goldmanns for some time.

In September 1944, Maximilián Goldmann and his sister Gizela with her little daughter asked the Lebdovič family for a shelter. Later, Dr. Fried with his wife, as well as Dr. Schick with his wife and three adult daughters, joined them. Ján Lebdovič prepared a shelter to hide them in a stable. It was a very complicated situation and therefore, after a short period of time, Gizela with her one-year-old son left the shelter. One day, Germans who were pulling back, put their horses in the stable and settled right in the house. Everybody lived in great fear until the moment when, fortunately, the Germans left.

The Lebdovič family took great care of their protégés. All those who were hiding there survived until the liberation at the end of January 1945. The actions of the rescuers were a result of their deep faith and love for people.

Wedding photograph of the Lebdovič family

Stable in a village of Mlynčeky in which the Lebdovič family hid the persecuted

Righteous Among the Nations since January 29, 2009

Vojtech KOLENKA

Saved the lives of:

Geza Spitzer, Pavol Spitzer, Jana Spitzerová, Juraj Spitzer, Michal Spitzer

Vojtech Kolenka, around 1943

Brothers Geza and Pavol Spitzer owned a colonial shop with delicacies in Poprad. From 1933 Vojtech Kolenka worked there as a salesman and he later aryanized the shop. He continued to act toward the Spitzers as if they were still the real owners of the business and when they were in danger he decided to help them. He initiated a meeting for Pavol Spitzer with Bishop Gojdič thanks to which both brothers would receive the presidential exemption. This was to protect both them and their relatives from deportation.

After the outbreak of the Slovak National Uprising, Pavol Spitzer decided to find shelter in the Low Tatras. Since Jana Spitzer's parents were elderly and would not have sustained hiding in the cool woods, Kolenka hid them in the house of his niece in Švábovce and later, in a sanatorium in the Tatras. After the suppression of SNU, eight members of the Spitzer family were still hiding in the attic of two lodges. On December 31, 1944, Germans surveyed the lodges but did not find anyone there. However, the next day the Germans came back and set both of them on fire. Meanwhile, the Spitzers dug a shelter in the deep forest. They were living in a tent for four weeks with a small supply of food. They were liberated in January 1945. After the war, the whole Spitzer family reunited. The Spitzer brothers renewed the shop in Poprad and made their rescuer, Vojtech Kolenka, their business partner.

One of the burned lodges

Vojtech Kolenka and Pavol Spitzer, around 1940

Geza Spitzer with his wife Cecilia

Vojtech Kolenka

Vojtech Kolenka and Marianna Spitzer, around 1936

Righteous Among the Nations since November 22, 2000

Andrej KOLESÁR • Zuzana KOLESÁROVÁ

Saved the lives of:

Alexander Blau, Regina Blauová, Maximilián Blau, Eugen Blau, Július Blau, Alicka Blauová

Andrej Kolesár lived in the village of Krásnovce, district of Michalovce. He had known the mechanic Alexander Blau since the time of their early childhood. They went to the same public school and were friends. After the Germans occupied Slovakia, the danger of deportation loomed over the Blau family, too. Alexander decided not to take risks.

Along with his wife Regina and their three children, a 10-year-old Alicka, 9-year-old Maximilián and 4-year-old Eugene, and also with Alexander's brother Július they left Michalovce to seek shelter in the villages. After several failed attempts, Alexander decided to go to Krásnovce to his childhood friend, who in the meantime had become also the father of two small children. Andrej Kolesár greeted them kindly and hid them all in the attic of his house. In the evenings, when Kolesár came to milk cows he provided his protégés with food prepared by Zuzana. The situation got complicated when a group of retreating German soldiers settled in Kolesár's house.

Andrej Kolesár with his first wife who died in childbirth

The hidden ones were lucky that this situation did not last for long, as the region of Michalovce was liberated by the Red Army before Christmas time. The rescuers and even more so the rescuees could finally relax, since it had not been easy for them to keep a 4-year-old child quiet and in the darkness.

Andrej Kolesár with his second wife Zuzana

Rescuers Andrej and Zuzana Kolesár with family

Kolesár's family

Righteous Among the Nations since December 4, 1996

Ján KRAJŇÁK • Mária KRAJŇÁKOVÁ

Saved the lives of: Zoltán Fleischer, Regina Fleischerová, Erika Fleischerová

During the deportation of Jews to Poland in 1942, the Fleischer family, father Zoltán, mother Regina, daughter Erika and the grandparents, were loaded into a wagon in Sabinov that took them to Prešov. There, before proceeding to Poland, one of their relatives submitted a falsified certificate of baptism to a Guardist, arguing that it was sent by Bishop Gojdič with an order to liberate the Fleischer family. With the exception of the grandparents, who continued on their way to doom, the family returned home.

After the outbreak of the uprising, they fled to the Levoča mountains, where they found a bunker in which several Jewish families had been already hiding. There they learned that citizens from the nearby villages are under the protection of a local priest willing to help persecuted people. Indeed, after connecting with inhabitants of Nižne Repaše, they began receiving food. In early October 1944, when the weather was starting to get cold, the Fleischer family left the bunker and went looking for a shelter in Nižne Repaše. By accident, they found Ján and Mária Krajňák, who at first hid them in the cellar and later in the attic of the barn. Every evening they brought food for six people in hiding. One day the Germans arrived there and they were almost discovered..

In January 1945, on the occasion of the Greek-Catholic Christmas Eve, all six "guests" were invited to dinner. During dinner, Fleischer asked Krajňák how much money he would want after the war for rescuing six lives. The answer was: "Yours as well as our rescue has been God's will which will be the reward for me." During the same month, the Soviet army liberated all of them.

"I clearly remember how we were gathered at school. All of our things were tied in blankets. Furthermore, I remember how we all had to go to the station and there we boarded a wagon, with just a board across to sit on. I was sitting in the arms of my grandmother. There were many people in the wagon. People were standing close to each other. The wagon closed, and I remember how they locked us in and the train started to move. It was on May 22, 1942. At one of the stations – now I know that it was in Prešov – the train stopped, the door opened and members of the HG or SS, I am not sure now, ordered my mother, father and me to get out. My grandparents stayed in the wagon. My cousin later told me that he had come to the station in Prešov and he approached members of the HG or SS as a messenger from Bishop Gojdič, and he showed proof of my baptism so that we were released."

Erika Fleischerová

Confirmation of release.

Baptism certificate of the Fleischers.

Certificate of a baptised Jew.

Righteous Among the Nations since October 22, 1998

Mária LAMPARTOVÁ • Ján LAMPART Salomea ZVOLINSKÁ

Saved the lives of: David Traurig, Serena Traurigová, Jozef Traurig

Dávid Traurig, later re-named Juraj Veselý was born and grew up in Stará Ľubovňa. During the persecution of Jews, he lived with forged documents in Michalovec and he married Serena Jozefovic. In the spring of 1943, they moved to Stará Ľubovňa, where at first they hid in the house of Salomea Zvolinská and later at her daughter's, Mária Lampartová.

Mária Lampartová, nee Zvolinská with her children

Mária was a very poor woman with six children and her husband went to work in the USA. The oldest son Ján helped his mother hide the Traurig family. At first they hid them in the granary in the yard but with the arrival of the first snow they moved them into the house. Traurig's brother Jozef also helped in hiding the couple. During the day he was in the granary and during the night he slept next to Ján in the room.

One night they were surprised by the arrival of Germans who were looking for hidden Jews. Josef was discovered and transported to a concentration camp in Sered', and from there to Auschwitz. He survived.

This event forced the Lamparts to think of a safer shelter for the Traurigs. Ján dug a hole under the stable, covered it with stumps and then he camouflaged the shelter. The depth of the hole enabled just lying or sitting at most. In this way they were hiding without movement and once a day, Mária brought them simple food.

With tears of joy everybody welcomed the end of the war. When Dávid and Serena finally got out of the hiding, they hugged and kissed Mária Lampart with a great deal of emotion. Mária told them it had been her human obligation to help and that she was extremely happy they had all survived.

After the war, there were some bad people who humiliated and slandered Mária. She accepted it with her head up because she was the only one who saved two human lives in Stará Ľubovňa.

"At one point, German soldiers moved into the barn with horses, and David and Serena were in the shelter. It was horrible! We were all crying at home, because we didn't know what was going to happen to them. It was rough then. Today it is hard to imagine how much fear we experienced then. There was just one punishment for hiding Jews. I remember that after that, my brother with my mother speculated about creating a safer shelter in the house, where they had a 'blind' spot behind a stove in a room where we lived. My brother made another wall behind that stove, and in that wall he left a hole through which we could give them food and they could use it to pull themselves out. We nailed a rack over it and we hung old coats on it, so soldiers couldn't see anything. On the opposite wall of the bunker there was also a small hole for Serena and Dávid to enable them to breathe. From the outside, we put shelves with pots, pans, bottles and so on. The small window was not visible, so it was always dark in the shelter and there was only enough place for two people. They suffered a lot, but we were glad that they didn't get sent to a concentration camp. We shared the fear and the bread."

*Mária Lampartová
Stará Ľubovňa*

Serena and Dávid Traurig

Righteous Among the Nations since January 27, 2010

Jozef BOROVSÝ · Eva BOROVSÁ

Saved the lives of:

**Dávid Gessler, Elek Gessler,
Lily Gesslerová, Roman Gessler**

Catholic priest Jozef Borovský and his wife Eva, actively helped persecuted people in their transition through the Carpathians. Jozef was at that time the parish administrator in Latorka village in Ruthenia (then part of Czechoslovakia). By the end of 1941, mass murders of Jews began in the valleys of death in Ukraine. Many of them, therefore, tried to escape through the Carpathians into Hungary where it was quite safe at that time.

David Gessler with his 14-year-old son Elek also asked for help. With the help of the Borovskýs, they successfully crossed the Hungarian border in January 1942. Two months later, after a difficult and demanding route, Elly, the Gessler's non-Jewish nanny of their children, an 8-year-old Lily and a 5-year-old Roman, also came to the Borovskýs. Eva Borovská warned them of the presence of Germans in the house at their arrival. After the danger had passed, they spent a few days together. Then they were escorted by Borovský into Mukachevo, where they took a train to Budapest, and the family reunited.

After war, in the early 1950s, the rescued Gessler tried to reconnect with his rescuers via a representative of Greek Catholic Church in Vienna. He did not recommend it because of the risk to priests in communist Czechoslovakia at that time. Borovský was later imprisoned and sent to forced labor for several years. Fearful of the regime he never told anyone about helping the Jews. His daughter Mary Borovská learned about the courage of her parents after their deaths.

The Borovskýs showed great courage in saving a Jewish family

The priest Jozef, his wife Eva and their friends in front of a parish building

Hiding place of the persecuted

Certificate giving the title Righteous Among the Nations by Yad Vashem to each of the awarded

Righteous Among the Nations since August 5, 1992

Ondrej MARADÍK with wife Martin MARADÍK · Elena MARADÍKOVÁ-FAKLOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

Martin Weil, Ján Kohol

John Martin Weil and Ján Kohol worked in a jewelry store in Prešov during the war. They lived together in a rented room in a house of the Maradík family who treated them as friends.

The father of the family was a police detective in Prešov and had access to sources of police information. When deportations started to increase, Andrew Maradík deleted the names of his Jewish tenants from Prešov police registration book.

On the day when members of the Hlinka Guard were rounding up Prešov Jews, the rescuers hid them in their yard and kept them informed about what was happening in the city. In the evening they found hiding for them in a house that belonged to another deported family. The apartment door was sealed and the Jewish youngsters crawled in through a tiny window. The Maradík family took care of their basic needs and food. After a few days they moved them onto the attic of their house, where they remained for the next two months. Later the Maradík family also helped other Jewish refugees who crossed the town on their way from Poland.

After the liberation, Weil returned to Prešov to thank his rescuers. He learned that Andrej Maradík, along with several police officers, had been arrested by the Gestapo and deported to Bergen Belsen, where they died. His wife died of grief a few years later.

Righteous Among the Nations since May 27, 1981

Ondrej MODLA · Anna MODLOVÁ – MARTINKOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

Edita Weitzenová, Edita Engländerová, Eduard Engländer

The family of the rescued Edita Weitzen lived in Kežmarok during the war. As refugees from the Sudeten area, they knew that they couldn't save themselves from forth-coming deportations of Jews to Poland. Therefore, the family decided to escape to Hungary. But the German invasion forced them to return to Kežmarok, Slovakia where their relatives, the Engländer family, lived.

Anna Modlová

Ján and Mária Modla were good neighbors to Engländer family. They hid their sixteen-year-old daughter Edith in their house and equipped her with documents of their own daughter. They dressed her in the type of clothes that were worn in the region and taught her the rules of Christian life and behavior. With these precautions they found her a job at the Baťa factory in nearby Batizovce.

Every Sunday Edita went "home" to rest, to be happy and take clean clothing. In the circle of a well-disposed family and with the job that they had found for her, Edita survived the toughest months of the war. There she also welcomed the day of liberation.

The Modlas hid Edith's uncle, Edward Engländer, his wife and their two children in the far off village of Lapaška, where they survived the war.

After the war, they immigrated to Israel. John Modla prematurely died and the rescuer Anna Modlová, later Martinková, was in the sixties sentenced to three years in prison for actions which did not suit the regime at that time.

Righteous Among the Nations since December 15, 1997

Michal MAŠLEJ

– his sermons encouraged his followers to help the persecuted Jews.

*Michal Mašlej
(first from the right)*

Michal Mašlej was a Greek Catholic priest in a remote village of Olšavica near Levoča. In his masses he encouraged the believers to help the persecuted, to feed the hungry and support the ones in need. When the hunt for partisans and Jews didn't exclude Olšavica, there was no one informer among the people. None of the hidden people were found although there were about 50 refugees, including 35 Jews, hiding there. Because the

Olšavica farmers were so devoted to their priest, he led them to believe that it is their human duty. Mašlej didn't only talk, but also took action. He was actively involved in hiding the Jews, helped them and gave them advice. In his priest's residence he accepted the Hartmann family from Sabínov. Among the refugees there was also the Fuchs family (later, the Filos) – father Ľudovít, mother Irena and their son Andrej from Stropkov. With the help of Mašlej they found a family, which was willing to take them, and he helped them with many other things. The family saw him as their guardian and savior.

With their approach to the front, a German military unit came to the village. Mašlej placed them with families who weren't hiding Jews at that time.

All hidden people in Olšavica survived until the liberation by the Red Army, on January 25, 1945. The rescued people provided testimony about the noble deeds of the priest Mašlej realizing these were the result of his deep religious beliefs, according to which charity is the supreme commandment of God.

In 1950 the state authorities banned Mašlej from clerical activity. In this difficult period of his life, faithful people showed him their devotion and support. After softening of religious persecution, he returned to his post in Olšavica, where he worked until his death in 1985.

*Michal Mašlej with his relatives
in the village of Olšavica*

Michal Mašlej during a mass

Righteous Among the Nations since May 6, 1997

Štefan PAVLÍK • Žofia PAVLÍKOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

**Husband and Wife Gelett
and their son Juraj (George) Geletty**

Štefan Pavlík

The couple Stefan and Zofia Pavlík lived in the village of Danišovce in the district of Spišská Nová Ves. They had known the pharmacist Geletty, who lived in Spišská Nová Ves, for a longer time. There was mutual respect and trust among them.

The Gelettys' fear of deportation in early September 1944, forced them to ask the Pavlíks to hide them. Štefan and Žofia didn't hesitate. They decided to hide the pharmacist Geletty, his wife and their 18-year-old son George in the attic of the farm. The constant fear of revelation that they were hiding a Jewish family was very stressful for both sides, almost unbearable. The Gelettys did not have enough strength to bear their heavy fate. For months they lived under huge pressure and often they did not even get to see the daylight. Poor physical condition and loss of faith in the early liberation had the Gelettys contemplating committing suicide, which fortunately failed.

Finally, the Gelettys couldn't stand to live in the attic any longer and they decided to return to their home in Spišská Nová Ves. They left their hiding place on December 17, 1944. To their surprise they found their 90-year-old aunt Bella Engel alive. Gestapo and the SS vacated one room in the house for her and left her alone. The Gelettys secretly joined her and remained there until the liberation by the Red Army on January 27, 1945.

Žofia Pavlíková

*The Pavlíks
with their son Michal*

The entrance to the attic

*Close to other houses, the Pavlíks
hid the Gelettys for several months
in the attic of the farm.*

*The original farm with a newer
extension of the Pavlíks house
in the village of Danišovce*

Righteous Among the Nations since July 8, 1996

Ján PIASECKÝ • Júlia PIASECKÁ • Anna PIASECKÁ

Saved the lives of:

Baruch Schwarz, Eljahu Schwartz, Cipora Halbersteinová

Ján Piasecký

Baruch and Eljahu Schwartz, natives of Stropkov, knew their rescuers from the time before the war. Eljahu enlisted in the Slovak army in 1939 as a soldier stripped of armament. In 1942, he received a farewell letter from his father. When he managed to get a pass, he returned home but his parents were no longer there. They were deported and the town was emptied of Jews. Eljahu decided to desert. He decided to ask the Piaseckýs to hide him.

He knocked on their door. Twelve-year old Anna reluctantly let him into the house. In the evening, after her parents returned from work, they clarified the cause of Anna's hesitation to Eljahu. They were already hiding one Jew in the house and they feared for his safety. He turned out to be nobody else but Eljahu's brother Baruch! They had already been hiding him in the grain room for several months. After Eljahu's arrival, Anna would warn them in moments of danger and delivered food to them.

Thanks to Janko, both brothers received Aryan documents. They worked for a short period of time and after the outbreak of the Slovak National Uprising in 1944, they joined the partisans. Baruch died and Eljahu fell into captivity and later died as well. These rescuers also provided shelter for Cipora Halberstamová, the daughter of the Stropkov Rabbi.

Anna Piasecká

Father Ján Piasecký. A photo of the awardee Júlia Piasecká hasn't been preserved.

Jozef TARABUS

Saved the lives of:

Dezider Kramer, Gizela Kramerová, Teodor Kramer

Dezider Kramer was employed in August 1942 in a working unit that repaired railroad tracks in Štrba. In early September, he received a secret report that the entire group was going to be concentrated, which meant the beginning of the preparations for their transportation.

Therefore, he decided to seek the assistance of his friend Jozef Tarabus even though he knew about his previous employment; he worked as a chief of the police station in Važec. Tarabus did not hesitate and he decided immediately to help his friend and his family.

He rented a small room for them in the attic of a little lonely home of the Hybeňs, who did not know their true identity. He visited them regularly and brought the necessary supplies. The Kramers remained in this hiding until the end of August 1944.

Righteous Among the Nations since September 12, 1993

Andrej SVATUŠKA • Mária SVATUŠKOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

Jon Davidovič, Mária Davidovičová, Margaréta Davidovičová, Ján Davidovič

Andrej Svatuška was a carpenter and his wife Mary was a housewife, and with their four children they lived a very modest life in Humenné. The Davidovič family lived in the neighborhood..

Margaret Davidovičová, was nineteen years old in the spring of 1942, when the hunt for Jewish girls began. On that day, when girls from Humenné were taken into transports, Margaret fled into the forest, accompanied by Mária Svatušková. After dark, they returned to the Svatuška house and it became a shelter for the persecuted. Andrej built an underground hiding place under the floor of the kitchen and Margareta retreated there in times of danger.

Two months later, deportations of the entire families began. At that point Margareta's parents joined her. The Svatuškas took care of all three of them.

Andrej and Mária Svatuškovci

The Davidovičs decided to leave for Nitra which proved to be fatal for them. During a raid on Jews, they were caught, deported and murdered. Their children Margaréta and Ján survived the war.

Mária Svatušková

The Svatuškas with their family in front of the house, in which the persecuted were hidden

The Svatuška Family

Righteous Among the Nations since March 29, 1999

Elisabeth STEPHANYOVÁ

Saved the lives of: **Marianka Fridrichová**

*Alžbeta Stephányová
along with the family
that sheltered them*

Elisabeth Stephanyová, later Alžbeta Stephányová, was born into a family who were part of the German minority in Gelnica. From 1937 until the end of her life she was closely connected to the family of Dr. Alexander Fridrich from Košice. When the Fridrichs had their daughter Judita, she began to work as their nanny and tutor. They called her Eržika. After the German invasion of Hungary in March 1944, Alexander Fridrich, along with other officials of the Jewish community, were taken into custody. In early May, the Fridrich family and the parents of his wife, Olga, were concentrated in a ghetto town where they awaited deportation.

Eržika continued to visit them regularly and brought them food in a basket. Once, on her way out of the ghetto, she hid and smuggled a four-month-old Marianna in the basket.

She suggested the Fridrichs to give her also their second daughter, Judita, but the Fridrichs refused. The mother was convinced that their seven-year-old daughter was strong enough to withstand the journey that awaited them. Later they were all deported.

Eržika with tiny Marianka left for Budapest to a Christian family, who were friends with the Fridrichs. However, the child's crying scared the family and Eržika was forced to leave. She reached a small village near the capital city, but had no address where she could go for help. Desperate, with a baby in her arms, she found herself on a bridge, where a man approached her and suggested she enter his house. This way, Eržika with Marianne found themselves in the house of Michal Lestyak, a landowner. She introduced herself as the mother of the girl and an escapee. She was allowed to remain in the house for which she compensated by work. The warm welcome they received from the family members at least somewhat eased their bitter fate.

Through the Red Cross, father Alexander, who was the only survivor of the family, succeeded in finding Eržika together with Marianna. He became the organizer of the emigration of Jews to Israel, and he himself was planning to leave at the end of 1949. A week before leaving, he was captured and sentenced to six full years in prison for preparing to emigrate. The authorities wanted to place Marianna in an orphanage, but Eržika took responsibility for her upbringing. When Marianna was 13 years old, her father was released from prison. Eržika continued to live in with the Fridrichs and after Marianna's marriage, she moved into the house of the young couple. After the occupation of Czechoslovakia (1968), Alexander, Marianna and her husband decided to emigrate to Germany. Eržika, despite great love for Marianna rejected the proposal claiming that her close ones were buried in Slovakia. The family maintained connection with her until her death in Košice in 1981.

*Alžbeta Stephányová
with Marianna Fridrich in 1947*

Righteous Among the Nations since July 14, 1996

Gustáv ŠVANCAR

Saved the lives of: **Harry Winkler, the Goregs, the Proppers, the Speisers**

Gustáv Švancar was employed by Artúr Propper, a Jew, who dealt with forestry. In the spring and summer of 1939, Jewish refugees from Germany asked Propper for help and he involved his employee Švancar in the rescue action. Propper asked him to transfer fourteen refugees to Poland.

The connection between Gustáv Švancar and Harry Winkler resulted from good neighbourhood relationship in Humenné. Henry Winkler's parents and six siblings were transported into a camp in 1942, where they died. Harry wasn't deported because at that time, he served in the so-called Sixth battalion. Later, Winkler obtained forged documents and lived illegally. The outbreak of the Slovak National Uprising and the German invasion into Slovakia in the autumn of 1944 forced him to return to Humenné. Humenné was full of German soldiers because it was located near the eastern front. He came to the city early in the morning and knocked on the window of his friend Gustav Švancar who provided him with a shelter. Winkler was looking for a solution that would not endanger his good friend. Harry learned about the partisan unit which operated in his district and he decided to join it. Gustáv didn't allow him to go by himself and he went with him up to the place where the unit was located – about 40 km from Humenné. Švancar also helped to rescue the families of Goregs, Proppers and Speisers, who survived the last days of the war in the village of Pokrivač.

Righteous Among the Nations since April 19, 1998

Václav BARTOŠEK • Štefánia BARTOŠEKOVÁ

Saved the lives of:

**Sára Grossbergová, Róza Grossbergová,
Leopold Grossberg, Ernest Grossberg, Móric Perloth**

In Kežmarok the Bartošeks and Grossbergs houses were situated opposite each other and there were friendly relationships between the families. It was a strange phenomenon in a town, where a lot of members of the German minority openly sympathized with the Nazi regime in Germany. Sára Grossbergová asked her neighbor Václav Bartošek to hide the members of her family. He agreed without any hesitation.

Her son-in-law Móric Perloth and her son Leopold Grossberg were among the first that were hidden. The next day, with the help of Eva – daughter of Bartošek – grandmother Sára and mother Róza joined them. The fifteen-year-old Eva ensured a safe passage into their hiding place. Son Ernest was hiding in another place, but thanks to Václav, the rescuer's son, he was also able to join his family.

The shelter was located in the attic. The entrance was from the kitchen and it was blocked by the cabinet. The winter of 1944-1945 was very rough. The rescuers moved their children to their bedroom, which allowed women and the youngest son Ernest to sleep in the kids' room. The rest, who were staying in the attic, were given warm blankets to prevent them from freezing under thin layer of roof tiles. Later an SS commander moved into the house but it did not discourage the rescuers from hiding their Jewish neighbors.

During the nights, when the situation appeared to be safe, they allowed the men to go down into the heated apartment from the attic, to warm up a bit and even listen to the allies radio broadcast. This was the situation for full five months, -- of constant fear and concern about their own safety and also for the rescuers, who did everything for them for purely humanistic motives.

Václav Bartošek

*Štefánia
Bartošeková*

Not all Slovaks who were awarded the Righteous Among the Nations award have been mentioned in this exhibition. It is only a fraction of the stories which happened during the dramatic years of the war. With the passing of time, some names of the rescuers and the rescued have been forgotten.

In Slovakia, more than 500 people were recognized and awarded the title of Righteous Among the Nations. We belong to the countries with the highest number of the awardees in proportion to the population.

To justify or rationalize various defects or even bad attitudes and actions, we tend to say that it is the era we live in or it was like that at the time. But that's just an excuse, because the era is created and defined by the people who live in it.

The rumors of mass killings and the meaning of "final solution of the Jewish question", a systematic, total extermination of a people – the Jews – left many with the inability to come to terms with this terrible reality. This was probably because the horrific events related to the Holocaust were the first of their kind in the history of mankind.

The Holocaust was the culmination of 19th century pogroms against the Jews. It defies understanding because of the enormous contradiction of human attitudes towards the laws of Nature and God's commandments. News about murdered Jews penetrated into the non-Jewish world, too. Its numeral and geographic range and especially its diabolic character in all countries that condemned Jews to a certain death, inspired kind-hearted people to try to save them. Not even the danger, to which they exposed themselves and their family members, discouraged them from doing so. In the testimonies of the rescued ones, a rescuer who appeared at the moments of victims' despair, was frequently compared to an angel from heaven. Nowadays, still, such people are the hope for mankind and a proof that good cannot be defeated.

Dr. Gila Fatranová

